

First records of the trypetine mining flies (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetini) from Ukraine

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Korneyev, V. A. & Korneyev, S. V. First Records of the Trypetine Mining Flies (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetini) from Ukraine. Abstract. Leaf mining trypetines *Hemilea dimidiata* (Costa, 1844), *Stemonocera spinifrons* (Schroeder, 1913), *Trypeta artemisiae* (Fabricius, 1794), and *T. immaculata* (Macquart, 1835) are recorded from Ukraine for the first time; data on their distribution and host plants in Europe are provided.

Key words: Diptera, Tephritidae, Trypetini, Ukraine, first records, distribution, host plants.

Корнеев, В. А. і Корнеев, С. В. Перші знахідки мінуючих мух-трипетин (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetini) з України. Резюме. Мухи-трипетини *Hemilea dimidiata* (Costa, 1844), *Stemonocera spinifrons* (Schroeder, 1913), *Trypeta artemisiae* (Fabricius, 1794) і *T. immaculata* (Macquart, 1835) вперше наведено з України; подано відомості про їхнє поширення у Європі та кормові рослини.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Tephritidae, Trypetini, Ukraine, перші знахідки, поширення, кормові рослини.

Корнеев, В. А. и Корнеев, С. В. Первые находки минирующих мух-трипетин (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetini) из Украины. Резюме. Минирующие мухи-трипетини *Hemilea dimidiata* (Costa, 1844), *Stemonocera spinifrons* (Schroeder, 1913), *Trypeta artemisiae* (Fabricius, 1794) и *T. immaculata* (Macquart, 1835) впервые указаны из Украины; приведены сведения об их распространении в Европе и кормовых растениях.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Tephritidae, Trypetini, Ukraine, первые находки, распространение, кормовые растения.

Introduction

The tribe Trypetini includes nearly 400 species of more than 45 genera, almost half of which occur in the East of the Palaearctic and, to the lesser degree, in the Oriental Region, with a few species in all other zoogeographical regions (Norrbom et al., 1999: 14). European fauna includes the subtribes Chetostomatina (genera *Anomoia* Walker, 1835, *Chetostoma* Rondani, 1856, and *Myoleja* Rondani, 1856), with four species (larvae fleshy-fruit eaters or inquilines in galls), and Trypetina (genera *Acidia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830, *Euleia* Walker, 1835, *Hemilea* Loew, 1862, *Philophylla* Rondani, 1870, *Platyparea* Loew, 1862, *Stemonocera* Rondani, 1870, and *Trypeta* Meigen, 1803), with sixteen species in Europe (Korneyev & Merz, 2004). Here, we consider *Anastrephoides* Hendel as

erroneously recorded from Europe (apparently based on a mislabelled specimen), and *Cryptaciura* Hendel, 1927 as a junior synonym of *Euleia* Walker, 1835, following Norrbom et al. (1999), and *Cornutrypeta* Han & Wang, 1993 as a junior synonym of *Stemonocera* (Merz, 1994: 111). Recently, one species of the Nearctic genus *Strauzia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 has been recorded from Germany as an invasive pest of sunflowers (Bruckner & Korneyev, 2010).

In Europe, most trypetines are restricted to humid zones, being associated mainly with mountains, from Atlas and Pyrenees to Alps, Carpatians and Caucasus, and the Forest Zone in the North East. A few species, such as *Euleia heraclei* (Linnaeus, 1758), which mines

various hogweeds and other mesophilous umbellate plants, *Anomoia purmunda* (Harris, 1778), breeding in the apples of hawthorns and related plants, and *Cotoneaster* widely used for hedges, often live in drier habitats. Some widespread species mine shade-loving weeds, as *Acidia cognata* (Wiedemann, 1817) on the coltsfoot *Tussilago farfara* and also on *Senecio* spp., *Philophylla caesio* (Harris, 1778) on the nettle (*Urtica dioica*), and *Trypeta artemisiae* (Fabricius, 1794) on mugwort (*Artemisia vulgaris*). Other species are often associated with river banks and shores, especially in the mountain regions of Middle Europe. Some of them have widely disjunct areals, occurring in Middle Europe and Caucasus (*Hemilea pulchella*), or Middle and Northern Europe and mountains of Central and Far Eastern Asia (*Stemonocera cornuta* (Scopoli, 1772), *S. spinifrons* (Schroeder, 1913), *S. superciliata* (Frey, 1835), *Trypeta artemisiae* (Fabricius, 1794), *T. immaculata* (Macquart, 1835).

Six species of Trypetini have been recorded by far from Ukraine: *Acidia cognata* (Wiedemann, 1817), *Anomoia purmunda* (Harris, 1778), *Euleia heraclei* (Linnaeus, 1758), *E. rotundiventris* (Fallén, 1820), *Philophylla caesio* (Harris, 1778), and *Trypeta zoe* Meigen, 1826 (Korneyev & Kameneva, 1985; Korneyev, 1987; Korneyev & Merz, 2004).

Recent re-identification of material added to the collection of the I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology (SIZK) revealed previously unpublished specimens of Trypetinae; in addition, a few species from neighboring countries have been found in other museums. All these species are recorded here for the first time.

Results

Hemilea dimidiata (Costa, 1844)

Material. Ukraine, Transcarpathian Region: Rakhiv, 27.06.2009, 1♀ (Yu. Gheriak) (SIZK).

Distribution. Austria, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Switzerland; Russia (Moscow Region, Caucasus); Turkey (Merz & Korneyev, 2004); Slovenia, Spain (Korneyev & Kolcsar, 2015); **Ukraine** (first record).

Host plants. Apparently, *Hieracium* spp., *Lactuca* spp., *Taraxacum* spp. or various other Cichorieae (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Stemonocera spinifrons (Schroeder, 1913)

Material. Ukraine, Transcarpathian Region: Rakhiv, 20.05.2009, 1♂ (Yu. Gheriak) (SIZK).

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom (Merz & Korneyev, 2004); Romania (Gheorgiu, 1986); Bulgaria (Korneyev & Kolcsar, 2015); Russia (Leningrad, Moscow Regions, Far East); Korean Peninsula (Korneyev, 1996).

Host plants. *Senecio fuchsii* and *Eupatorium cannabinum* (Merz, 1994).

Trypeta artemisiae (Fabricius, 1794)

Material. Ukraine, Kyiv, 5.06.1989, 1♂ (S. Zrazhevsky) (SIZK).

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, The Netherlands, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom (Merz & Korneyev, 2004); Russia (Leningrad, Moscow Region, West and East Siberia, Far East); Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, North-Eastern China, Korean Peninsula, Japan (Korneyev & Ovchinnikova, 2004); **Ukraine** (first record).

Host plants. *Achillea ptermica*, *Artemisia absinthium*, *A. vulgaris*, *Leucanthemum vulgare*, *Tanacetum vulgare*; also *Senecio vulgaris* and *Eupatorium cannabinum* are reported as host plants (Merz, 1994).

Trypeta immaculata (Macquart, 1835)

Material. Ukraine, Transcarpathian Region: Rakhiv, 2.06.2009, 1♀ (Yu. Gheriak) (SIZK).

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, The Netherlands, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom (Merz & Korneyev, 2004); Russia (European Part, West and East Siberia, Far East); ? China, Japan (Korneyev & Ovchinnikova, 2004); **Ukraine** (first record).

Host plants. Various Cichorieae (Asteraceae): *Hieracium* sp., *Hypochoeris* sp., *Lapsana* sp., *Leontodon* sp., *Mycelis muralis*, and *Taraxacum* sp. (Merz, 1994).

Trypeta zoe Meigen, 1826

Material. Ukraine, Kyiv Region: Irpin, 29.06.1979, 1♀ (M. Nesterov), idem, on *Artemisia vulgaris*, 18.06.1996, 3♀ (V. Korneyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom (Merz & Korneyev, 2004); Russia (European Territory, Far East) (Korneyev & Ovchinnikova, 2004).

Host plants. Larvae mine leaves of many Anthemideae and Senecioneae species, including *Artemisia* sp., *Leucanthemum* sp. and *Senecio* sp. (Merz, 1994).

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